

KAMBAG'ALLIK DARAJASINI O'LCHASH METODIKALARI

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JIDU, Xalqaro iqtisodiyot va menejment

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Hozirda kambag'allikni ikki turda o'chash keng tarqalganlari bular: kambag'allikni bir tomonlama (unidimensional) va ko'p tomonlama (multidimensional) o'lchash usullaridir.

Kambag'allikni bir tomonlama (unidimensional) o'lchash qashshoqlik o'lchovida faqat bir factorga tayanishdir. Kambag'allikni bir tomonlama o'lchashning asosiy 3 turi keng tarqalgan va umumjahon maydonda tan olinganlari daromadga asoslangan (Income based) o'lchov metodi, sarf harjatga asoslangan (Expenditure based) o'lchov metodi hamda Oziq ovqatdan olinadigan quvvatga asoslangan (Food energy intake (FEI)) o'lchov metodlaridir.

Daromadga va sarf harajatga asoslangan o'lchov medodlari o'z o'rnida kambag'allikning ikki turi asosiy va qiyosiy kambag'allikni o'lchaydi va o'lchovda kambag'allik chiqiqlaridan foydalaniladi.

Absolyut kambag'allik bu- hatto oziq-ovqat turar-joy, toza ichimlik suvi hamda ust-bosh kabi birlamchi ehtiyojlarga nisbatan ham yetarli mablag'ga ega emaslikdir. Rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda ushbu turdagi kambag'allik kategoriyasiga kuniga 1,9 dollardan kam pul ishlab topayotgan va sarflayotgan insonlar kiritiladi va ular absolyut kambag'allik chizig'i (absolyut poverty line) dan pastda turgan insonlar hisoblaniladi

Qiyosiy (relative) kambag'allik bu mamlakatdagi o'rta oylik daromad va sarf harajatdan 50-60% past daromat topish yoki sarflay olishdir. Rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda bu ko'rsatkich kuniga 3,1 dollardan kam pul ishlab toppish deb baholangan. Bu turdagi kambag'allik kategoriyasiga kiruvchilar hayot uchun zaruriy xarajatlarni amalga oshirishga qodir lekin ikkilamchi xarajatlar uchun ko'pincha pul sarflay olmaydi va yashash darajasi o'rta standartlarga nisbatan past bo'ladi.

Kambag'allikni oziq ovqatdan olinadigan quvvatga asoslangan holda o'lchash metodi ham mavjid, garchi bu metod nisbatan eskirgan bo'lsa ham hali hamaon ba'zi mamlakatlar uchun kambag'allik darajasini o'lchashda asosiy usul bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Bu usulda kambag'allik chizig'i kuniga 2,122 kaloriyadan kam ozuqa ovulchi aholi ustidan yotqiziladi. Ravallion va Bidali o'z maqolasida kambag'allik darajasini o'lchashda ishbu medodan foydalanmaslikni afzal deb

ko'rsatgan, chunki bu metod kiyim-kechak hamda bosh-pana singari boshqa birlamchi ehtiyojlarni o'zida mujassam etmaydi.

Kambag'allikni ko'p tomonlama o'lchash uslubi ya'ni multidimensional poverty index(MPI) xalqaro tan olingan kambag'allikni o'lchash uslubi bo'lib Oxford universiteti tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan. Bunday hisoblash uslubi an'anaviy kambag'allikni o'lchash uslublarini to'ldiradi ya'ni ko'proq informatsoiyalar bilan yoritadi. Ushbu uslubda inson imkoniyatlar (sifatli ta'lim, tibbiot, infratuzilma) va mol mulk (televizor, telefon, mashina, uy) va hokazolarga qanchalik egali o'rganiladi va shunga muvofiq kambag'allik indeksi shakllantiriladi.

MPI indekatorlarini quidagi suratdan ko'rishimiz mumkin (rasm 3) Indekatorlar asosiy 3 guruhga bo'lingan. Ular sog'liq, ta'lim va yashash standarti indekatorlari Ushbu indekatorlar ham o'z navbatida bir necha kategoriyalarga bo'lingan. Har bir kategoriya ma'lum miqdorda kambag'allik darajasini ifodalaydi. Misol uchun, ta'lim (2-jadval)

Sog'liq indekatori: Qachonki 70 yoshdan kichik inson yetarlicha kunlik ozuqa olmasa va 18 yoshdan kichik oila a'zolari orasida har besh yilda o'lim kuzatilsa bunday fuqorolar kambag'al hisoblaniladi. (2-jadval 1-2-qatorlar)

Ta'lim yo'nalishi kategoriyasini o'rganadigan bo'lsak qachonki oidalada hech bir fuqaro 6 yillik ta'lim ko'rmaga bo'lsa yoki 8-sinf gacha bo'lgan vaqtda biron marta maktabga bormagan bo'lsa oila kambag'allikga moyil bo'ladi.(2-jadval 3-4-qatorlar)

Yashash standartlari o'z navbatida 6 o'lchovni o'z ichiga olgan holda baholaniladi. Bunda oilalar taom pishirayotganda ishlanmagan yoqilg'idan foydalansalar msln tappi, o'tin, ko'mir, qishloq xo'jaligi hosillari, xonadonlar sanitariyik vositalardan hammon xojatxonadan mahrum bo'lsa, xo'jaliklar suv va elektr ta'minotidan mahrum bo'lsa, aholi uylari yashash standartlariga mso ta'mirlanmagan bo'lsa va nihoyat oilalar radio, televizor, velosiped, motosikl, mashina, muzlatgich kabi texnik vositalardan birontasiga ega bo'lmasa kambag'al deb hisoblaniladi.

Global Multidimensional Poverty Index: dimensions and indicators of poverty.

Source: OPHI (2018). [Global Multidimensional Poverty Index 2018: The Most Detailed Picture to Date of the World's Poorest People](#). Report. Oxford Poverty and Human Development Initiative, University of Oxford.

Kambag'allikni ko'p tomonlama baholash uslubi asosan global kambag'allikni tugatish bilan shug'illanuvchi xalqaro tashkilotlar tomonidan ishlatiladi. Quidagi jadvalning 4-ustunidan ko'rinib turibdiki, kambag'allik omillari yechimi Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkilotining Davomiy Rivohlanish Maqsadlari (SDGs)ga kiritilgan

DIMENSION OF POVERTY	INDICATOR	DEPRIVED IF LIVING IN A HAUSHOLD WHERE...	SDG AREA
Health(1/3)	Nutrition	Any person under 70 years of age for whom there is nutritional information is undernourished .	SDG 2: Zero Hunger
	Child mortality	A child under 18 has died in the household in the five-year period preceding the survey.	SDG 3: Health and Well-being
Education (1/3)	Years of schooling	No eligible household member has completed six years of schooling .	SDG 4: Quality Education

	School attendance	Any school-aged child is not attending school up to the age at which he/she would complete class 8 .	SDG 4: Quality education
Living Standards (1/3)	Cooking fuel	A household cooks using solid fuel , such as dung, agricultural crop, shrubs, wood, charcoal, or coal.	SDG 7: Affordable and Clean Energy
	Sanitation	The household has unimproved or no sanitation facility or it is improved but shared with other households.	SDG 6: Clean water and Sanitation
	Drinking water	The household's source of drinking water is not safe or safe drinking water is a 30-minute or longer walk from home, roundtrip.	SDG 6: Clean water and Sanitation
	Electricity	The household has no electricity .	SDG 7: Affordable and Clean Energy
	Assets	The household does not own more than one of these assets : radio, TV, telephone, computer, animal cart, bicycle, motorbike, or refrigerator, and does not own a car or truck.	SDG 1: No poverty

Source: Alkire, S., Kanagaratnam, U. and Suppa, N. (2020). 'The global Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI): 2020 revision', OPHI MPI Methodological Note 49, Oxford Poverty and Human Development Initiative, University of Oxford